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Shifts in research priorities in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) during COVID-19 times

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has struck LAC exceptionally hard, having substantial health, social and economic consequences for the population living in this region. As of 27 April 2022, there have been at least 68 million people infected (~13% of world share) and 1.68 million reported deaths (~25% of world share) associated with the novel coronavirus in the region, while LAC represents less than 8.5% of World population.¹

While the health and social impacts of COVID-19 in LAC are relatively well understood at this stage, less is known about the response of LAC researchers towards the pandemic. COVID-19 has attracted tremendous interest from researchers worldwide, resulting in a considerable body of COVID-19 literature being published in a relatively short period. Given the urgent need for evidence to support clinical and public health decisions, the evolution of this new research field showed unprecedented growth rates (Coccia, 2021; Else, 2020), also in comparison with previous pandemics (Bryan et al., 2021; Ioannidis et al., 2021), which have advanced discoveries and new approaches including innovative types of drugs (e.g. mRNA vaccines), diagnostics (e.g. telehealth), technologies (e.g. applications to monitor confinement) and societal responses (e.g. response and effect of confinement policies) (Tuttle, 2020).

In a context of global efforts across countries and international research funders, the research share from LAC authors have been relatively scarce, with estimates between 1% and 3% of the global research share, depending on the indexing system (e.g. PubMed, Web of Science (WoS), Scopus, bioRxiv, medRxiv) and period being used (Fiesco-Sepúlveda & Serrano-Bermúdez, 2020; Wang & Tian, 2021). Moreover, it has been argued that more emphasis in the region has been on epidemiologic/surveillance studies than vaccines/therapeutics or interventional studies (Espinosa et al., 2021; Mansilla et al., 2022).

It is also well known that the COVID-19 pandemic also influenced publication dynamics in non-COVID-19 research. Using simulation models, it was been estimated that the COVID pandemic was associated with an 18% decrease in the production of non-COVID-19 research in the World (Raynaud et al., 2021). However, little is known about changes in research priorities in LAC and if the research that has been conducted in LAC in response to the COVID-19 crisis accounts for the impact that the pandemic is having in the region. In a global study, Agarwal and Gaule (2022) show that the R&D response to COVID-19 (clinical trials) in the World has been 4 to 26 times greater than that implied by its market size, defined as the

¹ <https://graphics.reuters.com/world-coronavirus-tracker-and-maps/regions/latin-america-and-the-caribbean/>

mortality of the disease weighted by the GDP per capita where those deaths occurred. This is an unprecedented global R&D response that shows that research priorities and innovation may be shifted towards societal challenges.

Approach and Data

Approach

This paper aims to study the evolution of scientific activities in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), during the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) crisis. Our main research question is to understand how the specialisation of LAC research shifted during the COVID-19 crisis.

Given that scientists are a key source of ideas that drive economic development, it is important to analyse changes in the direction of research priorities (Myers, 2020; Stephan, 2012). We will first analyse trends in research production in all LAC countries per OECD major research area in WoS between 2000 and 2021, and then create a new COVID-19 area based on a query that will help to assess the impact of COVID-19 crisis on LAC research specialisation. Then, we will use a persistent digital identifier (ORCID) to analyse what were the areas that the most prolific COVID-19 researchers were working on before they shifted to COVID-19 related research. This will help us understand which capabilities were relevant for COVID-19 related research, and which research area lost research production due to the pandemic.

Data

Publication data were extracted from the Web of Science (WoS)² (2022) and a robustness check was done using Dimensions (2022). We made a preliminary analysis of the coverage of four different indexing systems (WoS, Dimensions, Scopus, ScIELO and PubMed) having in mind the objectives of our study, and we decided on WoS (and InCites) due to its reliability, quality data regarding affiliations and research area classification procedures.

As for what we consider to be scientific publications related to “COVID-19”, estimates differ depending on search terms, database coverage, and definitions of what counts as a scientific publication. This paper uses two approaches to identify COVID-19 related research: i) query-based approach³; ii) citation topics approach⁴. In both approaches, we only count as “scientific publication” articles and reviews that are published in journals indexed to WoS (Core Collection + ESCI) and Dimensions. Although there was a “torrent” of COVID-19 related research released during 2020 and 2021 that was posted as preprints on platforms such as “medRxiv” or “arXiv” (Else, 2020), we choose not to include those publications since they are not peer-reviewed, and there are have been concerns about the quality and validity of COVID-19 research in general (Horbach, 2021; Jung et al., 2021; London & Kimmelman, 2020) which should be worst in non-peer-reviewed research. In this paper, we use the “Citation Topics” (macro, meso and micro) from InCites to analyse in more detail which topics increased (decreased) more between 2018-2019 and 2020-2021.⁵ These topics are created based on citation relations between publications (Waltman & Van Eck, 2012; Waltman, van Eck, & Noyons, 2010). Since one of the micro-topics is “coronavirus”, we use this topic as an alternative

² Web of Science Core Collection + Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI)

³ Query: (“Covid19” OR “COVID 2019” OR “coronavirus 2019” OR “coronavirus disease 2019” OR “2019 nCoV” OR “SARS nCoV” OR “SARS-CoV-2” OR “Wuhan coronavirus” OR “Wuhan pneumonia” OR “novel coronavirus”) AND PY = (2019 OR 2020 OR 2021).

⁴ <https://clarivate.com/blog/introducing-citation-topics/>

⁵ We also use the six broad OECD subject areas (‘Agricultural Sciences’, ‘Engineering and Technology’, ‘Medical and Health Sciences’, ‘Natural Sciences’, ‘Social Sciences’ and ‘Humanities’), which is a standard mapping of all science to compare the size of COVID-19 related research in relation to these broad research areas.

proxy to our query-based approach, to identify all COVID-19 related research during 2020 and 2021. The “Citation Topics” from InCites are divided into three hierarchical schemes (10 broad macro-topics, 326 meso-topics and 2444 micro-topics). We take advantage of this structure to analyse how scientists in LAC responded to the COVID-19 pandemic between 2018-2019 and 2020-2021. We first identify all ORCID IDs of LAC researchers that published a COVID-19 (query-based approach) related publication during 2019-2021. This allowed us to identify a total of 11683 ORCID IDs that produced at least one COVID-19 publication that includes a LAC author. Please note that not all 11683 authors are from LAC since these publications also include their foreign co-authors. For our analysis, we only use the 141 ORCID IDs that produced five or more (>4) COVID-19 publications and have a LAC affiliation as their latest affiliation. A similar approach was also used by Ioannidis et al. (2021). Our top 141 verified ORCID IDs produced 723 pubs (~13.6%) of total COVID-19 pubs in the region (2019-2021). We use this set of publications and authors to understand the dynamics of change in research trajectories of LAC researchers before and after COVID-19.

Results

Trends in LAC COVID-19 research production

At the beginning of 2020, it became clear to practically everyone in the world that more information on COVID-19 and related topics were one of the most important things in the world for scientists to work on. The scientific community in LAC also responded.

In Fig. 1 we apply the query-based approach (i), to analyse the expansion of publications related to COVID-19 by LAC authors monthly. We observe that production spiked since February 2020 both in WoS and Dimensions. In WoS, we identified 5302 publications (6.24% of all COVID-19 related publications in WoS) and in Dimensions 11198 publications (3.12% of all COVID-19 related publications in Dimensions). We find that the growth rates only started to increase after February 2020, three months after the first known case was identified in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. In WoS, the plateau was reached in September 2020 (200-300 publications per month) and in Dimensions the plateau was reached a bit earlier in May-June 2020 (400-550 publications). WoS and Dimensions have significantly different journal coverage, with WoS being the most selective and Dimensions being the most comprehensive. This partially explains the higher number of COVID-19 publications in Dimensions.

Figure 1. Trends in COVID-19 research in LAC (WoS & Dimensions). 2020-2021

Source: WoS (Core Collection + ESCI), Dimensions

Note 1: Articles and reviews only

To compare the relative size of this expansion in relation to other broad research areas, we analyse trends in research production in LAC using the six OECD areas. In Figure 2, we find that during 2020-2021 COVID-19 related research represented 1.9% of all LAC research in WoS (1.2% in 2020 and 2.6% in 2021). For comparison, in Dimensions, COVID-19 related research represented 2.7% of all LAC research (2.2% in 2020 and 3.2% in 2021). Between 2018-2019 and 2020-2021, the major OECD areas declines in LAC happened in “Humanities” (6.8% to 5.7%), “Social Sciences” (17.7% to 16.3%) and “Agricultural Sciences” (11.6% to 11%). Surprisingly, “Medical and Health Sciences” research share didn’t decline significantly in LAC between 2018-2019 and 2020-2021. We were expecting it to decline, because our hypothesis was that researchers in this area would be closer to the “research space” (Guevara et al., 2016) of COVID-19 and there would be larger trade-offs within this area. However, we also tested this conjecture using a different subject area scheme (Macro Citation Topics), and we obtain a similar non-declining pattern for “Clinical and Life Sciences” during 2020-2021.

Figure 2. Trends in LAC research per OECD research area (6 + COVID-19). 2000-2021

Source: WoS (Core Collection + ESCI)

Note 1: Articles and reviews only.

Note 2: Publications are associated with OECD research areas based on their journals. Journals might have more than one OECD research area. COVID-19 publications are based on a Query. We checked what are the OECD research areas of COVID-19 publications and subtracted them from the OECD research areas count.

COVID-19 authors' research trajectories

The COVID-19 pandemic is a rare instance of a large discrete shift in global medical needs, and thus of research trajectories for scientists. This allows us to examine how the scientific landscape changed in response to the COVID-19 shock.

Given that very few researchers were studying coronaviruses before 2020, the arrival of COVID-19 called upon scientists across research areas to consider a directional change in their research. By using the Micro Citation Topics in InCites we identified that during 2010-2019 there were 135 pubs from LAC researchers related to the “coronavirus” micro-citation topic. In 2020-2021 this number jumped to 2440 publications, representing around 1% of all LAC

research during this period.⁶ This shift offers an opportunity to study the adaptability of science and, in the case of LAC, to understand which research capabilities were more relevant in the region to the new pandemic.

We first identify all ORCIDiDs of LAC researchers that published a COVID-19 related publication during 2019-2021. Then, we use algorithms and manual search methods to identify the most productive ORCIDiDs in LAC. We end up with 141 ORCIDiDs that we use to understand which areas were more relevant for COVID-19 research and the size of the “shift”. The countries of these 141 authors were Brazil (n = 93), Mexico (n = 27), Chile (n = 6), Ecuador (n= 5), Colombia (n = 3), Peru (n = 3), Argentina (n = 2), Honduras (n = 1) and Venezuela (n = 1). It is relevant to emphasize that these 141 researchers were likely among the most productive before the pandemic. Therefore, this is not a representative sample of COVID-19 LAC researchers but a sample of competitive researchers that were quick in moving into a rapidly emerging research area.

These 141 ORCIDiDs produced 1909 publications in 2018-2019 (2 years before COVID-19) and 2942 publications in 2020-2021, in all areas. In 2018-2019, 81% of their research was related to the macro-topic “Clinical & Life Sciences”, 12% to “Agriculture, Environment & Ecology”, 5% to “Chemistry”, 1% to “Social Sciences” and 1% to other research areas.

In our analysis, we also look in more detail at the meso and micro-topics where these researchers came from. In Fig. 3 the top 10 meso-topics with more researchers are:

1. Virology - Tropical Diseases (7%)
2. Assisted Ventilation (5%)
3. Sports Science (5%)
4. Phytochemicals (4%)
5. Nutrition & Dietetics (3%)
6. Immunology (3%)
7. Antibiotics & Antimicrobials (3%)
8. Allergy (2%)
9. 9. HIV (2%)
10. Obstetrics & Gynecology (2%)

⁶ Please note that our “query-based approach” is more comprehensive in identifying COVID-19 related publications

Figure 3. Top meso-topics for top141 “COVID-19 researchers” in LAC in 18-19
Top areas of "covid researchers" in LAC - 2018-2019

The appearance in the top 10 of some areas such as “Virology - Tropical Diseases”, “Assisted Ventilation”, “Immunology”, and “HIV” is not surprising given that the capabilities developed by these researchers are related and potentially relevant for COVID-19.

LAC is a region that suffers from several tropical diseases such as Dengue, Chagas, Zika and Malaria. Therefore, it was expected that this is one of the meso-topics (“Virology - Tropical Diseases”) where more researchers came from. A significant micro topic within this meso topic is “Dengue”. Dengue fever is a mosquito-borne tropical disease caused by the dengue virus which is highly prevalent in Latin America. In 2019, more than 5 million people were infected with the disease across the world. According to Chen et al. (2022), in most countries, COVID-19-related disruption led to historically low dengue incidence in 2020.

During the pandemic, the use of assisted (mechanical) ventilation became very common to treat COVID-19 patients with respiratory failure. Therefore, it is also natural that “assisted ventilation” was one of the meso-topics in which more researchers specialised before starting to produce COVID-19 related research. “Nutrition & Dietetics”, “Immunology”, “Antibiotics & Antimicrobials”, “Allergy” are also meso-topics with high potential to contribute to COVID-19 research in areas related to prevention, immune response, treatments, and interactions with other diseases/conditions.

“HIV” (human immunodeficiency virus) is a retrovirus that might lead to late symptoms of infection referred to as acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS). HIV/AIDS is also considered a pandemic and has killed almost 33 million people worldwide. COVID-19 only killed a fraction of that (~6 million), however, it has been far more disruptive to societies and economies, since the virus is transmitted more readily through everyday contacts and so most countries performed lockdowns to prevent the spread. HIV/AIDS has been a public health concern for LAC due to a remaining prevalence of the disease. In 2018 an estimated 2.2 million people had HIV in LAC, making the HIV prevalence rate approximately 0.4% in Latin America.⁷ HIV/AIDS is one of the diseases with the highest number of publications in LAC, with a much higher output than other more endogenous (and neglected) diseases such as dengue or zika (Fontecha, Sánchez, & Ortiz, 2021). Although being different epidemics, some of the experiences learned from HIV had the potential to be used for COVID-19 such as building clear

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HIV/AIDS_in_Latin_America

frameworks for the response, action-oriented communication to stimulate behaviour change, and building scoreboards and frameworks relevant for accountability.⁸

From these top 10, only “Phytochemicals” (compounds that are produced by plants) is related to “Agriculture, Environment & Ecology”. This outlier is probably related to the antiviral potential that compounds coming from plants (e.g. vascular) have for the treatment of COVID-19 (e.g. Españo et al., 2021; Swain et al., 2021).

All other nine micro areas from the top 10 belong to the Macro Citation Topic “Clinical & Life Sciences”. However, some of these nine meso-topics seem remote from COVID-19, e.g. “Sports Science”, “Obstetrics & Gynecology”. We also found experts specializing in their past work on distant topics such as “Paper & Wood Materials Science”, “Dairy & Animal Sciences”, “Photoproductivity” and “Nanoparticles” which published COVID-19 research during 2020-2021. This indicates that there was sufficient flexibility from these scholars to make large jumps from their prior research work probably due to career incentives (Hill et al., 2021).

We are also interested in dynamics of change, namely which areas “lost” research production due to the COVID-19 pandemic. To understand “switches” we analyse which meso-topics of the 141 ORCIDs lost research share between 18-19 and 20-21.

Figure 4. Top 25 meso-topics for top141 “COVID-19 researchers” in LAC in 18-19

Overall, we found that there was not a significant sacrifice of research effort across research areas and some of these meso topics actually increased more than 50% between periods (e.g. “Nutrition & Dietetics”, “Immunology”, “Healthcare Policy”). Some notable exceptions include “Sports Science”, “Assisted Ventilation” and “Stem Cell Research”, that lost more than 25% of their publications in 2018-2019.

⁸ https://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/media_asset/lessons-hiv-prevention-covid19_en.pdf

Discussion

Science has, since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic, never looked so important to the everyday lives of people everywhere. The characterization of the virus; development of tests for infection; therapeutics to reduce the severity of the disease; information infrastructure to track the spreading; use of epidemiological models to predict the consequences of interventions; and the development of vaccines—all are dependent on scientific expertise and capability. Most countries have benefited from the pre-existence of a strong scientific and technical research base to this pandemic. The scientific community in LAC also responded massively to the pandemic. Between 2020-2021 COVID-19 related papers represented 6% of all COVID-19 related research in the World and between 2 and 3% of total scientific output (all areas) in the region. Before 2020, we could only identify in WoS 135 papers related to “coronavirus” by LAC authors. In 2020-2021 we identified 5302 COVID-19 related publications in WoS (40x more). In comparison, the topic with the second highest growth rate between 2018-2019 and 2020-2021 is “Microplastics” which increased 109% (1x) between periods.

We identified the 141 researchers from LAC that were very prolific (5 or more pubs) in publishing COVID-19 related research publications in 2020-2021 and represented around 14% of total COVID-19 in the region. Overall, we found that the research areas where the most productive COVID-19 LAC researchers came from were highly related and relevant for COVID-19 (e.g. “Virology - Tropical Diseases”, “Assisted Ventilation”, “Immunology”, and “HIV”). This indicates that, as expected, when a new crisis emerges the scholars better able to produce new knowledge related to an emergent issue are the ones closer to the research space of that new research area. We found some exceptions that made large switches in their research areas (e.g. “Sports Science”, “Obstetrics & Gynecology”), which also reveals that the scientific community has sufficient flexibility to shift attention rapidly to major issues if there are clear incentives. Most of these switches were done without significantly sacrificing research effort on other research areas. Some notable exceptions include “Sports Science”, “Assisted Ventilation” and “Stem Cell Research”, that lost more than 25% of their publications in 2018-2019.

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